

POSITION OF NATURAL CAPITAL TODAY

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Abstract In the era of modernization of the world economy, the transition to many updated innovative technologies, the driving force of development is the efficiency factor of the economy. - is implemented by attracting public and private investments in economic activities, infrastructure and assets that prevent the loss of diversity and ecosystem services. Today, issues of achieving innovative development, modernization of the economy, rational use of limited resources at the maximum level are among the important tasks that must be carried out not only for the national economy but also for the entire world community. Because of this, the "green" strategies implemented by the countries are being supported today.

Keywords: green zone, green economy, greening efforts, greening strategy, branches of green economy.

Implementation of the State Program on the implementation of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of supporting active entrepreneurship, innovative ideas and technologies", as well as the recreation park and improving their activities by attracting investments due to the introduction of public-private partnerships in their use [1].

In recent years, environmental degradation (climate change, desertification, loss of biodiversity), depletion of natural capital, increasing poverty, shortages of fresh water, food, and energy, people and countries Problems such as inequality between the two are the reasons why the current economic system is not perfect.

Global crises all exacerbate pressing socioeconomic challenges to stability in both developed and developing countries, such as job losses, social insecurity, and poverty. The current state of the world, irreparable ecological catastrophes and enormous damage to the environment require the need to transition to a "green economy". If we pay attention, we can see that the world's leading countries have already started the transition to a green economy. They have already realized that the green economy cannot replace sustainable development but is a way to achieve sustainable development.

The essence of sustainable development is that the current generation should organize its economic activities in such a way that the next generations should have economic opportunities and living well-being no less than them.

It is not allowed to expand and build new industrial, utility warehouses and other facilities that are not directly related to the use of recreational facilities in the areas of green zones and protected natural areas [2].

Buildings and structures serving the farm and agriculture in the suburbs of the city are allowed to be located within the green zones.

Zones are formed by artificial landscaping and the preservation of natural landscapes [2].

Today's problems such as scarcity of resources, environmental problems and economic risks are studied in the research works of A.V. Vakhobov, Sh.Kh. Khajibakiyev, Sh.A. Tashmatov, M.T. Butaboyev. [3] In their scientific works and scientific literature, it is noted that such problems can be achieved only by transitioning to a green economy.

Foreign economists studied the theoretical and practical aspects of the development of the "green economy" - scientists William Hynes, Shannon Wang, Erik Solheim, Patricia, Ardakanian, Dirk Jaeger.

Foreign economists, representatives of the CIS T.V. Zakharova, Valentin Pchelintsev, Tatyana Kruglikova, Irina Zhivotovskaya, Tatyana Chernomorova, Tkachenko Aleksandr Aleksandrovich and others emphasized the necessity of transition to a green economy and its high impact on the country's development.

The green economy is an economic system aimed at reducing the resources necessary for human life and health, environmental risks and environmental scarcity, and developing all areas of the economy without damaging the environment. We will not be mistaken if we associate the green economy with the ecological economy, but it is a new direction that is more politically used.

Scarcity of resources - the lack of resources that satisfy the needs of a person during his life is called a phenomenon of resource scarcity.

The scarcity of resources is an age-old and unsolved problem of humanity, and the imbalance between unlimited human needs and limited resources is the main problem of the economy.

It seems to me that after the industrial revolution, there was a lack of respect for natural resources. I can give an example of water shortage, depletion of underground and surface resources, food shortage, the limited number of the working population, lack of energy resources, etc. Some resources can be restored. For example, it is possible to create a new garden by planting new trees instead of cutting trees. Even if it takes years. But minerals are non-renewable resources.

In the next 200 years, the number of consumers on the globe increased 5 times, but the land surface and natural resources did not increase. Climate change is also intensifying. 72% of the Earth's surface consists of oceans, and several parts of the land are uninhabitable. Addressing such problems must be accompanied by strategies that promote economic growth, and meet various social needs such as education, health, social protection and job creation while combating environmental pollution and addressing climate change. has become a strategic goal of the economy.

Green growth is a special strategy for sustainable development. It provides a way to combat environmental problems and use natural resources. This study examines the impact of green technology and environmental factors on green growth in countries with the high gross domestic product (GDP) from 2000 to 2020.¹ In addition, it examines the linear and exponential relationship between GDP and green growth. For this, we use an advanced econometric approach. The

result shows that the linear effect of GDP is positive for green growth. Conversely, the non-linear effect of GDP has a negative magnitude for green growth. In addition, green technology significantly increases green growth. Energy consumption is an important influencing factor and it reduces green growth. Environmental factors also reduce green growth in the sample countries, according to the findings. It should be noted that the combined effect of energy consumption and emissions undermines green growth in countries. Based on the empirical findings, this study suggests policymakers that countries with high GDP should manage their economic and environmental activities to increase the amount of green growth that can protect the environment.

Issues of transition to a "green economy" are expressed in most strategic development documents of the EU. According to the analysis, "green economy" is not used as a main concept or a priority direction in ensuring sustainable development. Nevertheless, a "green economy" is considered one of the ways of integrating the priorities of sustainable development. Employment and development are among the measures to combat climate change.

In the last decade, the concept of a "Green Economy" has emerged as a strategic priority for many governments and intergovernmental organizations.

In total, 65 countries have developed Green Economies and related strategies. They will be prepared to address the major challenges of the 21st century, from resource scarcity to climate change and economic volatility.

If we answer the question, why transition to a green economy is necessary? A green economy brings prosperity to the people of the earth and reduces the level of poverty. A high level of human development in all countries, whether it is in education or health care, serves to create the opportunity to achieve what is necessary for a person to live a comfortable life.

The green economy helps to restore biodiversity, prevent negative changes in ecology and protect the environment. The content of sustainable development is that the current generation should organize their economic activities in such a way

that the next generations have economic opportunities and livelihoods that are no less than theirs. It is manifested because they should have well-being.

Currently, there is an urgent need to transition to an economic model that will increase human well-being, preserve resources, and ensure that they do not expose future generations to serious environmental risks. We can achieve economic well-being and prevent future generations from facing economic and social problems and environmental risks only in solidarity.

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